

Extracellular vesicles positive for markers of endothelial dysfunction and senescence in ESRD patients: Implications for gender-specific survival

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End-stage renal disease (ESRD) is often associated with cardiovascular complications and premature mortality. The pathophysiological processes of endothelial cell injury involve mechanisms which result in increased production of extracellular vesicles (EVs). EVs are recently identified circulating biomarkers that are related to cellular senescence and endothelial dysfunction. The aim of the study was to examine the levels of EVs positive for markers of endothelial dysfunction and senescence in ESRD patients and evaluate their impact on survival, with a focus on gender-specific differences. This case study included 76 hemodialysis patients who were followed for 36 months. The concentration of EVs positive for markers of endothelial inflammation (MCP-1 and E-selectin) and senescence (FUCA and p16) was assessed by digital flow cytometry in serum of ESRD patients. The obtained results have shown that EVs positive for markers of endothelial inflammation significantly influenced both overall and cardiovascular survival in a total number of patients. According to Kaplan Meier analysis, the impact of elevated levels of MCP-1⁺EVs and E-selectin⁺EVs on shorter overall survival was more pronounced in female patients (p=0.011 and p=0.001, respectively) compared to their male counterparts (p=0.447 and p=0.420, respectively). Similarly, elevated levels of FUCA⁺EVs influenced significantly worse overall survival in female patients (p=0.037), but had no effect on male patients (p=0.871). EVs bearing markers of endothelial dysfunction and senescence might serve as prognostic indicators in ESRD patients. The greater impact of assessed EVs on survival observed in female patients suggests the potential need for gender-specific medical approach in managing ESRD.

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